

Analysis of *Pyricularia grisea* populations from three different blast epidemics

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In spite of a great deal of research on the blast pathogen (*Pyricularia grisea* (Cooke) Sacc., an anamorph of *Magnaporthe grisea* (T.T. Herbert) Yaegashi & Udegawa) of rice and the disease itself, blast remains a serious constraint to rice production in areas with conducive environments and where susceptible cultivars are grown. There has been no effort to analyze the pathogen populations that occurred during the blast epidemics in India. Three of these epidemics occurred in the state of Orissa in the past decade. The first epidemic was in Banki, Cuttack District, in the 1997 wet season, during which traditional rice cultivars Laghubhutia and Golabondi were heavily infected by neck blast. The second epidemic, in the wet season of 2000 in Dhenkanal, Dhenkanal District, involved traditional cultivar Latamohu and high-yielding semidwarf Dhala Heera. They got severely infected by leaf blast. During the third epidemic (2002 wet season, Ganjam District), high-yielding variety Swarna grown in farmers' fields was severely infected by leaf blast.

A repetitive element-based polymerase chain reaction (rep-PCR), with primer sequences from Pot2 (an element found in approximately 100 copies in the *P. grisea* genome), provides an efficient way to monitor the population dynamics of the blast pathogen. This method is compa-

table with that determined with MGR586 restriction fragment length polymorphism lineages (George et al 1998). Our analysis clearly brought out the population structure of the pathogen in the three blast epidemics and showed the difference between traditional and modern rice cultivars.

Three sets of monoconidial isolates of the pathogen *P. grisea* were obtained from infected leaf/neck blast samples collected from farmers' fields during the epidemics. Totalling 103, these were stored on filter paper bits at -20°C and were used for DNA fingerprinting (Table 1). Genomic DNA was extracted following the procedure of Murray and Thompson (1980) for plant DNA with modifications for mini-scale preparation as described by Scott et al (1993). Polymerase chain reaction with primers Pot2-1 (5' CGGAAGCCCTAAAGCTGTTT 3') and Pot2-2 (5' CCCTCATTC-GTCACACGTTC 3') and visualization of the DNA fragments were as described previously (George et al 1998). The gel images were photographed using a gel documentation system equipped with Bio-Capt software (Vilber Lourmat, France). The structure of the pathogen population was analyzed using the Bio-1D++ software (Vilber Lourmat, France). For each band position between 400 bp and 23 kb, the presence or absence of the band

was indicated by this software in a computer for each isolate. The binary matrix indicating presence or absence of the bands was used to construct a matrix of similarities between all pairs of isolates based on Dice's coefficient ($F = 2N_{xy} / (N_x + N_y)$), where N_{xy} is the total number of bands observed for that pair of isolates.

Fingerprint patterns of *P. grisea* subpopulations from Banki (29 isolates), Dhenkanal (31 isolates), and Berhampur (43 isolates) revealed the presence of 23, 24, and 43 haplotypes, respectively. The Banki population was differentiated into three lineages of the pathogen at 60% similarity (Fig. 1a). Two of the lineages detected were obtained from a single cultivar, Golabondi, whereas the third lineage was obtained from the other cultivar, Laghubhutia. However, one of the isolates obtained from the former cultivar belonged to the third lineage. The Dhenkanal population obtained from two rice cultivars (Dhala Heera and Latamohu) was grouped into four lineages of the blast pathogen (Fig. 1b). All the isolates belonging to the first three lineages were obtained from Dhala Heera, which is a modern semidwarf variety, while the isolates of the fourth lineage were obtained from Latamohu, which is a traditional rice cultivar. The subpopulation of the pathogen isolates obtained from the blast epidemic in Berhampur was dif-

ferentiated into 12 lineages (Fig. 1c). Interestingly, all the isolates of the subpopulation of the pathogen were obtained from a single modern rice cultivar, Swarna, which was the predominant variety in farmers' fields in this location. In general, traditional rice varieties were infected by a single predominant lineage of the pathogen during epidemics, whereas modern rice cultivars were infected by multiple lineages of the blast pathogen (Fig. 2).

References

- George MLC, Nelson RJ, Zeigler RS, Leung H. 1998. Rapid population analysis of *Magnaporthe grisea* with rep-PCR using endogenous repetitive DNA sequences. *Phytopathology* 88:223-229.
- Murray MG, Thompson WF. 1980. Rapid isolation of high molecular weight plant DNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 8:4321-4325.
- Scott RP, Zeigler RS, Nelson RJ. 1993. A procedure for miniscale preparation of *Pyricularia grisea* DNA. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 18(1): 47-48.

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Fig. 1. Dendrogram constructed with UPGMA on the basis of Pot2 repetitive element-based polymerase chain reaction fingerprint data of *Pyricularia grisea* for a collection of 29 isolates from two rice cultivars: Golabondi (isolates: IAPG 0101–IAPG 0115) and Laghubhutia (isolates: IAPG 0116–IAPG 0129) grown in Banki (a); 31 isolates from two rice cultivars: Latamohu (isolates: IAPG 0130–IAPG 0145) and Dhala Heera (isolates: IAPG 0146–IAPG 0160) grown in Dhenkanal (b); and 43 isolates from a single rice cultivar Swarna (isolates: IAPG 0161–IAPG 0203) grown in Berhampur (c). Homology level of 60% is marked with broken lines vertically.

Fig. 2. Occurrence of different blast pathogen lineages in three different blast epidemic outbreaks at Banki, Dhenkanal, and Berhampur in the state of Orissa.

Isolates of *Pyricularia grisea* collected from farmers' fields in epidemic regions for comparative study.

Site	District in Orissa	Ecosystem	Season ^a	Rice genotypes	No. of isolates		
					Tissue		Total
					Leaf	Neck	
Banki	Cuttack	Rainfed upland	1997 WS	Laghubhutia and Golabondi	–	29	29
Dhenkanal	Dhenkanal	Rainfed upland	2000 WS	Latamohu and Dhala Heera	31	–	31
Berhampur	Ganjam	Rainfed upland	2002 WS	Swarna	43	–	43
Total					74	29	103

^aWS = wet season.

Record of a hyperparasitoid on *Pseudogonatopus nudus* Perkins (Dryinidae: Chrysidoidea) parasitizing *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) from Asia

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Plant- and leafhoppers of rice are well-recognized noxious pests and severe populations have often caused serious rice yield losses. Many natural enemies are reported on these hoppers in rice. Among the parasitoids, mymarids and trichogrammatids

are the most common. The rest of the parasitoids, dryinids, pipunculids, strepsipterans, and vellids, are unstable but still contribute to the biological management of hoppers.

In a routine attempt to collect dryinids, parasitized brown

planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) nymphs and adults showing the larval sac protrusion symptom were collected during the 2004 Kuruwai crop (July-Sep). They were transferred to potted plants under greenhouse conditions and reared till